

after transplanting – just as adult beetles were migrating from adjacent heavily infested fields and beginning to infest the crop.

Carbofuran-treated plots had no *D.*

armigera population throughout the 30-day experimental period (see table) and yielded the highest (2.3 t/ha), although the insecticidal treatments did not give statistically different yields. The

minimum number of damaged leaves was found in the carbofuran treatment, but treatments again did not differ significantly. Thiodemeton gave the highest net profit (\$56.02/ha). ■

Influence of ammonium phosphate levels on rice leaf roller incidence

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The rice leaf roller *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée (Lepidoptera; Pyralidae) seriously damaged rice plants in a fertilizer experimental plot at Ubon Rice Experiment Station, Rice Fertilizer Branch (Rice Division), in northeastern Thailand during the 1979 wet season. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications and 14 ammonium phosphate (16-20-0) levels. Twenty-eight-day-old seedlings of RD2 rice were transplanted in 3- x 5-m plots. Half the fertilizer with 37.5 kg K₂O/ha was basally applied and the rest was applied 30 days after transplanting.

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer levels on rice leaf folder damage, Ubon Rice Experiment Station, Thailand, 1979.

Nitrogen treatment (kg/ha)	Damaged leaves ^a 52 DT (%)
0	5.4 a
15	9.4 ab
30	10.2 ab
45	14.1 abc
60	12.8 abc
75	22.9 bcd
90	26.5 cd
105	33.2 d
120	34.3 d
135	33.1 d
150	52.8 e
165	62.2 e
180	56.9 e
195	64.2 e
C.V. = 37.0%	

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level (LSD). DT = days after transplanting.

The leaves damaged by the leaf roller and those undamaged on 30 hills randomly selected from each plot were counted.

The result showed that the percentages of damaged leaves rose proportionally with increasing nitrogen levels from 0 to 195 kg N/ha (see table). At 0 nitrogen the damaged leaves were only 5.34% while at 195 kg N/ha the damage was greatest (64.2%). The percentage of damaged leaves sharply increased at 75 kg N/ha level and was significantly different from that in the untreated control treatment.

Increased outbreaks of the rice leaf roller and other rice insects in recent years were believed related to increased use of nitrogenous fertilizer among farmers. How nitrogenous fertilizer affects the insect is not known. It has been reported the insect would oviposit more on dark-green rice plants than on greenish or yellow ones. ■

Soil and crop management

Effect of liming on the control of green algae in blue-green algae multiplication fields

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Green alga (GA) is a problem in paddy fields because it chokes the crop in initial stages, retarding tillering and removing considerable quantities of applied nitrogen. GA are becoming a problem in fields where blue-green algae (BGA) are multiplied. GA appear earlier and grow more luxuriantly in red or sandy soils than in clay soils. Lime, which is commonly used to control GA, was tested for algae control in BGA multiplication units.

Superphosphate fertilizer was applied

at 50 g/m². For pest control 25 g of carbofuran 3% G was applied to each plot. Water was maintained continuously at 5 cm. The field was rich in BGA

inoculum, so no fresh seed material was applied. Lime was applied at 1,250 - 10,000 kg/ha with graded increases of 1,250/kg. The BGA yield was measured

Yield of blue-green algae (BGA) and information on it and on green algae (GA). Aduthurai, India.

Levels of lime (kg/ha)	BGA yield (kg/m ²)	Appearance of GA (days after experiment initiation)	Types ^a of RGA in descending order of abundance
1,250	0.64	23	Ao, Ad, M1, Cm, Afu
2,500	0.52	21	Ao, Cm, M1, Ad, Afu
3,750	0.42	18	Ao, Ad, M1, Cm
5,000	0.29	16	Ao, Ad, M1
6,250	0.16	13	M1, Ao, Ad
7,500	0.10	10	M1, Ao
8,750	0.07	9	M1
10,000	0.05	9	M1
Control	0.17	28	Ao, Ad, M1, Afu
CD	0.055		

^aAd = *Anabaena doliolum*, Afu = *Anabaena fuelleborni*, Ao = *Anabaena oscillarioides*, Cm = *Cylindrospermum muscicola*, M1 = *Microcoleus lacustris*.

on the 20th day (see table).

Even low lime levels of 1,250 kg/ha inhibited BGA growth significantly; BGA inhibition increased as lime increased.

Contrary to general belief, lime application did not control GA in the BGA multiplication units (see table). ■

Response of rice varieties to zinc treatment in farmers' fields at DND irrigation project, BWDB, Bangladesh

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Zinc deficiency in Bangladesh rice fields seems to be more acute in the irrigated areas (where the lands are kept wet for longer periods than in other areas) and in calcareous soils. In 1979, zinc deficiency was suspected in the BRRI-BWDB collaborative cropping systems research site at Shimrail in the DND irrigation project of the BWDB. A superimposed zinc treatment used 2% ZnO solution as seedling dip for 4 rice varieties grown by farmers in the area. Crop-cuts were made and grain yields adjusted at 14% moisture to determine the effect of zinc treatment on grain yield. IR8 responded tremendously to zinc treatment, yielding an extra 1.1 t/ha over the control (see table). The response of the local varieties to zinc application, in terms of increased grain yield, was only 0.1 t/ha. Studies on the problem are being continued. ■

Effect of dipping roots of rice seedlings in 2% ZnO on yield at Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra irrigation project, BWDB, 1979 transplanted aman season, Bangladesh.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	With zinc	Without zinc	Difference
IR8 ^a	3.8	2.7	1.1
Pajam ^b	3.0	2.9	0.1
Nizersail ^b	3.4	3.3	0.1
Pagu ^c	3.2	3.1	0.1

^aAv of trials in 3 plots. ^bAv of trials in 2 plots.

^c Trial in 1 plot.

Role of direct-seeded rice in Sudan Gezira crop rotation

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Rice is cultivated in the Sudan Gezira as an irrigated, direct-seeded crop in a four-course rotation (cotton-wheat-groundnuts-fallow). Although the role of rice in this rotation has not been investigated in depth, the current practice is to grow rice instead of groundnuts or fallow. Apparently, this practice is not very appropriate because numerous studies carried out at GRS have shown that the soil nitrogen content is usually too low to sustain a rice crop under these conditions, considering the high nitrogen losses in this environment. Therefore, relatively high rates of nitrogen fertilizers are required to attain high rice yields; 140 kg N/ha is considered as the optimum level for rice. Furthermore, there are some indications that a preceding crop does not influence rice performance solely through its effects on soil nitrogen content but, even more important, through effects on soil physical and chemical characteristics.

IR2053-206-1-3-6 was grown at seven

nitrogen levels after phillipesara, sesame, and fallow at GRS for three seasons, 1977-79. The nitrogen treatments were arranged in four replications in a randomized complete block design.

Rice yields increased progressively and significantly ($P = 0.001$) with increased nitrogen levels up to 160 kg N/ha. Beyond that level, yield increases were nonsignificant. But rice yield potentials differed greatly: 7.0 t/ha after sesame, 6.1 t/ha after phillipesara, and 5.0 t/ha after fallow. The increases in grain yield with an increase in applied nitrogen were generally similar in each rotation. The beneficial effects of sesame as an excellent precursor to other crops in the Sudan's central rain lands and of phillipesara in the Gezira were well established. From extrapolation of the results (see figure), it appears that only phillipesara increased soil nitrogen content. But because the application of higher nitrogen levels did not compensate for the differences in observed yield potentials, a preceding crop's influence on rice may be due to other physical or chemical soil properties. Integration of rice in a suitable rotation currently dominated by other crops is an important consideration. ■

Response of IR2053-206-1-3-6 grown as irrigated direct-seeded crop after phillipesara, sesame, and fallow at different nitrogen levels. Gezira Research Station, Sudan, 1977-79.